

A Multi-Metric Evaluation Framework for Selecting Tabular Synthetic Data Generators in Healthcare

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Abstract—Synthetic data generation is increasingly adopted in healthcare to facilitate data sharing while preserving privacy. However, the quality of synthetic tabular data varies substantially across generation methods and data characteristics. In this work, synthetic data generated by four widely used tabular generators (Gaussian Copula, CTGAN, TVAE, and a mixture-based BGMMOCE) are evaluated on a clinical tabular dataset. Data quality is assessed using a combination of SDV-based metrics and statistical similarity measures, capturing distributional fidelity, multivariate relationships, and potential privacy risks. Our results demonstrate that generator performance differs across evaluation dimensions, highlighting the absence of a universally optimal method. To support informed and context-aware generator selection, an agent is further introduced that reasons over relevant scientific literature alongside empirical evaluation outcomes to recommend the most suitable synthetic data generator for the given dataset. This study emphasizes the importance of systematic multi-metric evaluation and evidence-based selection of synthetic data generation methods in healthcare.

Index Terms—synthetic data, tabular data, data quality evaluation, statistical similarity, agent

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I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, synthetic data have become widely used in machine learning and data analysis due to advantages such as privacy preservation, reduced data access barriers and the ability to simulate complex scenarios [1]. In healthcare, synthetic tabular data provide a practical alternative to sensitive patient-level datasets, enabling methodological development and evaluation while mitigating privacy and governance constraints [1].

The performance of synthetic tabular data generators is highly dependent on dataset characteristics, including sample size, missing values, feature heterogeneity, class imbalance and the presence of complex statistical dependencies [2]. As a result, a generator that performs well on one dataset may fail to adequately capture distributions or relationships in another, rendering synthetic data quality inherently context-dependent [3]. Moreover, reliance on a single evaluation criterion may provide an incomplete or misleading assessment of generator performance, motivating the use of multi-metric evaluation frameworks [4].

Importantly, synthetic tabular data generators rely on distinct modeling assumptions, which directly influence their performance across datasets. Statistical approaches, such as Gaussian Copula models, offer transparency but are limited in capturing complex non-linear relationships, while deep generative models, including GANs and VAEs, can model

richer dependencies at the cost of increased training sensitivity and reduced interpretability [5]. Mixture-based methods aim to represent data heterogeneity through latent components, but may struggle with sparse or highly imbalanced categorical features [6]. Consequently, generator performance depends on the alignment between model assumptions and dataset characteristics, motivating systematic evaluation and context-aware selection strategies [5], [6].

In this work, a comparative evaluation of synthetic tabular data generated by four widely used methods, Gaussian Copula, CTGAN, TVAE, and a mixture-based BGMMOCE, is presented. The generated datasets are assessed using SDV quality reports in conjunction with additional statistical similarity measures, enabling an extensive evaluation of univariate distributions and multivariate relationships. Beyond quantitative assessment, a literature informed agent is introduced to support evidence driven generator selection. The agent reasons over relevant scientific publications alongside empirical evaluation outcomes to provide recommendations tailored to dataset characteristics. Rather than proposing a single optimal generator, this approach aims to facilitate transparent and informed selection of synthetic data generation methods for healthcare applications.

From a technical perspective, this study advances the evaluation of synthetic tabular data by jointly considering distributional fidelity, dependency preservation, and privacy-related risks within a unified assessment perspective. The inclusion of an agentic component further enables empirical evaluation outcomes to be interpreted in the context of prior scientific evidence, supporting principled and context-aware generator selection. From a clinical perspective, the proposed approach promotes safer and more transparent use of synthetic tabular data in healthcare research, where generator choice may influence both analytical validity and privacy protection. By prioritizing context-aware selection over the notion of a universally optimal generator, this work aligns synthetic data evaluation with the practical constraints of real-world clinical datasets.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

The study is conducted on a clinical tabular dataset consisting of 971 patient records described by 65 features, including continuous, categorical and binary variables. The dataset comprises 439 Healthy individuals, 260 patients with Non-Advanced Adenomas (NAA), 216 with Advanced Adenomas (AA) and 56 diagnosed with Colorectal Cancer (CRC). The data are split into 80% training and 20% test subsets. The training subset is used to fit the synthetic data generators and to perform statistical quality evaluation through distributional and structural similarity measures. The test subset is reserved exclusively for privacy-related assessment, enabling evaluation of potential disclosure risks. Identical preprocessing steps, including data cleaning and type-consistent encoding, are applied across all generators to ensure a fair comparison.

B. Synthetic Data Generation

Synthetic tabular datasets were generated using four representative methods: Gaussian Copula Synthesizer (GCS), CTGAN, TVAE, and the mixture-based BGMMOCE model. For deep generative models, the number of training epochs was selected based on empirical evaluation of synthetic data quality and observed convergence behavior, while all other hyperparameters were retained at their default values to avoid confounding effects. Specifically, CTGAN was trained for 300 epochs and TVAE for 750 epochs, which yielded stable training and improved quality metrics. All generators were applied to the same preprocessed real dataset to ensure consistency and fair comparison across methods.

Gaussian Copula (GC) is a statistical generative model that preserves marginal distributions and pairwise dependencies by modeling correlations through a Gaussian copula, serving as a classical baseline for tabular synthetic data generation [7]. CTGAN is a GAN-based model designed to capture complex, non-linear relationships in mixed-type tabular data, particularly in the presence of categorical features [8]. TVAE is a variational autoencoder tailored for tabular data that learns a probabilistic latent representation to generate synthetic samples while preserving key statistical properties [9]. Finally, BGMMOCE is a mixture-based approach that models joint distributions using Gaussian mixture models with automatically estimated components, enabling the representation of multivariate dependencies in structured healthcare datasets [10].

Briefly, a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) assumes that the observed data $\mathbf{X} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\}$ are generated from a mixture of K Gaussian components, with probability function:

$$p(x | \theta) = \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \mathcal{N}(x | \mu_k, \Sigma_k) \quad (1)$$

where π_k represents the mixing weight of the k -th Gaussian component, $\mathcal{N}(x | \mu_k, \Sigma_k)$ denotes the corresponding Gaussian density, and θ collectively refers to the model parameters [11]. Model fitting aims to determine the parameter set θ that maximizes the log-likelihood of the observed data, denoted as $\log L(\theta; \mathbf{X})$:

$$\log L(\theta; \mathbf{X}) = \sum_{i=1}^N \log p(x_i | \theta) \quad (2)$$

using the Expectation–Maximization (EM) algorithm. However, the EM algorithm may struggle to capture complex data topologies due to its reliance on a fixed number of mixture components, sensitivity to initialization, and the risk of overfitting or underfitting in high-dimensional or complex data settings [12]. To mitigate these limitations, BGMMOCE extends the GMM framework by incorporating variational inference together with a Dirichlet Process (DP), allowing the number of Gaussian components to be adaptively determined as the optimal set of clusters that best represent the underlying data structure [11], [12].

A unified metadata schema is defined and used across all generators, where applicable, specifying variable types and constraints to preserve the semantic structure of the original data. Continuous, categorical, and ordinal features are treated consistently across models, and identical training data are provided to each generator. For each generator, synthetic samples are generated using the training subset of the real dataset and matched in size to the corresponding training split. This design choice ensures that differences observed in subsequent evaluation stages can be attributed to the underlying generative mechanisms rather than variations in sample size or potential data leakage.

C. Evaluation methods

The evaluation workflow used in this study is summarized in Fig. 1. Synthetic datasets generated by each method are assessed using quality, statistical similarity and privacy-related metrics to enable multi-dimensional assessment.

Fig. 1. Agentic AI-based workflow for statistical evaluation and selection of synthetic data generators.

Data quality evaluation is conducted using the Synthetic Data Vault (SDV) library, a Python framework for synthetic data generation and evaluation. SDV quality reports are performed to evaluate the fidelity of univariate feature distributions and the preservation of multivariate relationships between real and synthetic datasets [13].

To complement SDV-based evaluation, additional statistical similarity metrics are applied, including the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for continuous variables, the chi-square test for categorical distributions, total variation distance (TVD), and the correlation-based error metrics. These measures provide distributional and dependency-based perspectives beyond a single quality score.

Privacy-related statistics are computed exclusively on the test subset to assess potential disclosure risks, ensuring separation between data used for synthetic data generation and data used for privacy evaluation.

D. The proposed Agentic AI-based workflow

The proposed agent is designed as a lightweight, literature-informed decision support component rather than an evaluation or data generator mechanism. The agent was implemented using a locally deployed large language model based on Qwen3, accessed via the Ollama runtime, enabling lightweight, reproducible inference without reliance on external cloud services.

It is provided with a curated set of five representative research papers on synthetic tabular data generation and evaluation, together with summary characteristics of the target dataset, including data type composition and observed empirical evaluation outcomes.

Fig. 2. Implementation architecture of the proposed agent.

As illustrated in Fig. 2, the agent performs a qualitative reasoning process that aligns dataset properties and empirical findings with insights reported in the literature. The agent output consists of a context-aware recommendation indicating the most suitable synthetic data generator for the given dataset, accompanied by a brief justification grounded in prior research and observed metric behavior.

Importantly, the agent does not introduce new evaluation metrics, perform model training or conduct additional quantitative analysis. Its role is to support informed generator selection by synthesizing empirical results and domain knowledge, thereby facilitating transparent and reproducible decision-making.

III. RESULTS

A. SDV Quality Evaluation

Table I summarizes the SDV quality scores obtained for each synthetic data generator. CTGAN achieves the highest overall quality score, driven by strong performance in both column shape fidelity and column pair trend preservation. BGMMOCE and GCS demonstrate comparable overall quality, while TVAE shows reduced performance in capturing multivariate relationships, as reflected in lower column pair trend scores.

TABLE I
SDV QUALITY SCORE

Model	Column Shapes	Column Pair Trends	Score
GCS	89.53%	82.55%	86.04%
CTGAN	90.80%	87.45%	89.13%
TVAE	90.01%	77.95%	83.98%
BGMMOCE	91.01%	80.64%	85.82%

B. Statistical Similarity Metrics

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) statistic evaluates the alignment of continuous feature distributions between real and synthetic data [14]. As shown in Table II, TVAE achieves the lowest mean KS value, indicating a strong preservation

of univariate continuous marginals. BGMMOCE and GCS exhibit higher KS values, while CTGAN shows the largest deviation, consistent with reported challenges of GAN-based models in precisely matching marginal distributions.

Categorical similarity is assessed using the chi-square distance and total variation distance (TVD) [15], [16]. GCS demonstrates the lowest values across both metrics, reflecting close alignment with real categorical distributions. CTGAN shows moderate divergence, whereas TVAE presents higher categorical discrepancies, highlighting trade-offs between categorical marginal fidelity and other aspects of data quality. Although BGMMOCE exhibits a substantially higher chi-square distance, this effect reflects the sensitivity of the χ^2 statistic to sparse and imbalanced categorical distributions, while TVD provides a more bounded and interpretable measure of categorical divergence.

Correlation MAE quantifies the deviation between real and synthetic feature–feature correlations [17]. GCS achieves the lowest MAE correlation, closely followed by BGMMOCE, indicating improved preservation of multivariate dependencies. In contrast, CTGAN and TVAE exhibit higher correlation errors, suggesting weaker alignment of dependency structures despite competitive performance in univariate metrics.

TABLE II
STATISTICAL SIMILARITY METRICS

Model	KS (avg)↓	χ^2 (avg)↓	TVD↓	Corr. MAE↓
GCS	0.2101	1.9547	0.0141	0.0626
CTGAN	0.2584	15.6343	0.0467	0.0801
TVAE	0.0944	55.3006	0.0787	0.0868
BGMMOCE	0.1591	340.9577	0.0791	0.0716

To complement the quantitative evaluation, Fig. 2 provides a visual comparison of real and synthetic data distributions for two representative continuous features generated by CTGAN. These kernel density estimates offer insight into feature-specific differences in marginal fidelity, illustrating trade-offs that may not be fully captured by numerical metrics alone.

Fig. 3. Distribution of two indicative features (gray: real data, magenta: CTGAN’s synthetic data).

C. Privacy Metrics

All privacy metrics were computed on the held-out test subset to avoid bias arising from training data reuse and to ensure a realistic assessment of disclosure risk. Table III summarizes privacy-related evaluation results across the examined generators. Disclosure Protection Estimate values indicate

generally strong resistance to attribute disclosure, with BGMMOCE and CTGAN achieving the highest scores, followed closely by GCS, while TVAE exhibits comparatively lower protection. Overfitting risk, assessed via DCR Overfitting Protection, follows a similar trend, with BGMMOCE and CTGAN yielding higher scores, suggesting reduced memorization of training data and improved separation between training and test samples. Overall, these findings indicate that privacy preservation varies across generators and does not necessarily align with statistical similarity performance, highlighting the importance of jointly considering privacy and utility metrics when selecting synthetic data generation methods.

TABLE III
PRIVACY METRICS

Model	Disclosure Protection Estimate	DCR Overfitting Protection
GCS	0.8935	0.2088
CTGAN	0.9129	0.2758
TVAE	0.7684	0.2113
BGMMOCE	0.9406	0.3196

D. Agent Recommendations

Based on the summarized dataset characteristics and a curated set of relevant studies on synthetic tabular data generation and evaluation, the literature-informed agent identifies CTGAN as a suitable generator for the examined dataset due to its ability to model complex conditional dependencies, address imbalanced categorical variables through conditional sampling, and accommodate non-Gaussian continuous distributions via mode-specific normalization. This recommendation reflects a balance between statistical fidelity and privacy preservation rather than dominance across individual evaluation metrics. The agent output is intended to support informed decision-making and does not replace empirical evaluation results.

IV. DISCUSSION

The experimental results demonstrate that no single synthetic data generator consistently dominates across all evaluation metrics. While certain models exhibit strong performance in preserving univariate distributions, others better capture multivariate dependencies or provide improved privacy protection. These findings highlight the dataset-dependent nature of synthetic data generation and confirm that generator performance varies according to the specific characteristics of the data and the evaluation criteria considered.

The observed discrepancies across statistical similarity and privacy metrics illustrate inherent trade-offs between data fidelity and privacy preservation. Models achieving closer alignment with real data distributions may exhibit increased overfitting risk, whereas generators with stronger privacy guaranteed may sacrifice aspects of distributional or structural accuracy. This reinforces the necessity of evaluating synthetic data using multiple complementary metrics rather than relying on a single quality score.

In addition to statistical similarity and privacy evaluation, an exploratory bias characterization was conducted to provide contextual insight into the underlying dataset. The analysis indicated the presence of moderate pre-existing subgroup imbalances between sex and diagnosis categories, primarily reflected in distributional differences rather than strong global dependence. Qualitative inspection of the synthetic datasets suggested that generators differed in their tendency to preserve or attenuate these associations, with some models implicitly smoothing conditional relationships present in the source data. This behavior does not constitute bias mitigation, but rather reflects trade-offs between fidelity to the original data structure and distributional regularization. These observations further emphasize the dataset-dependent nature of synthetic data generation and underscore the importance of context-aware interpretation when evaluating and selecting generators.

Within this context, the proposed literature-informed agent provides practical value by supporting context-aware generator selection. Instead of identifying a universally optimal method, the agent integrates empirical evaluation outcomes with insights from relevant research to guide informed decision-making based on dataset properties and application priorities. Such an approach is particularly relevant in healthcare settings, where both utility and privacy considerations are critical.

This study focuses on a single real-world clinical tabular dataset to enable a controlled and interpretable comparison across synthetic data generators. Hyperparameter tuning is limited to basic training configuration choices, such as the number of training epochs, while all other parameters were kept fixed to avoid confounding effects. The evaluation emphasizes statistical similarity and privacy preservation, without assessing downstream task performance. These design choices define the scope of the present work and motivate future extensions to additional datasets, task-specific utility evaluation, and adaptive tuning strategies.

From a technical standpoint, this study demonstrates the value of combining multi-metric evaluation with agentic reasoning to support principled interpretation of synthetic data quality and privacy trade-offs. By contextualizing empirical evaluation results using scientific evidence, the proposed approach moves beyond isolated metric reporting and enables more informed and transparent generator selection decisions.

From a clinical standpoint, the findings highlight the importance of careful synthetic data generator selection in healthcare applications, where subtle distortions in data structure or privacy leakage may have downstream analytical or interpretability consequences. The proposed agentic workflow provides a practical mechanism for aligning synthetic data generation strategies with clinical data characteristics and privacy requirements, thereby supporting more responsible adoption of synthetic data methodologies in clinical research.

V. CONCLUSION

This study presents a systematic evaluation of synthetic tabular data generation methods for healthcare applications, combining statistical similarity and privacy-related metrics to

assess generator performance. The results demonstrate that synthetic data quality is highly context-dependent, with no single generator consistently excelling across all evaluation criteria. These findings underscore the importance of multi-metric assessment frameworks for capturing complementary aspects of data fidelity and disclosure risk.

To support informed generator selection, a literature-informed agent is introduced to integrate empirical evaluation outcomes with domain knowledge, providing context-aware recommendations rather than a single optimal choice. This approach promotes transparent and evidence-based decision-making, which is particularly critical in sensitive healthcare settings. Future work will extend this framework to additional datasets, incorporate task-specific utility evaluation, and explore adaptive configuration strategies to further refine synthetic data generation and selection.

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